

On the Ignition Temperature of Some Gases.

BY HEMENDRA KUMAR SEN AND HARENDRA NATH CHATTERJEE.

Whilst one of us (H.K.S.) was called upon to investigate a basement explosion some time ago, our attention was drawn to an interesting work of McDavid (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, **111**, 1003) who determined the ignition temperatures of a few gas mixtures by enclosing them in soap bubbles and touching them by means of a heated block or glowing spiral. The great divergence between the results obtained by McDavid and those by others is no doubt due to the method followed by individual workers to cause the ignition, and the irreproducibility of his own figures using different sources of ignition clearly indicates the futility of attempting to establish ignition temperature as a physical constant. From the practical point of view, however, the stationary method of ignition, as introduced in McDavid's work, is of considerable importance, but the determination of the lowest ignition temperatures under such circumstances is of still greater consequence. The present work has been, therefore, confined to the investigation of this latter point by firing gas mixtures enclosed in soap bubbles of different dimensions.

The difficulty, if not the impossibility, of obtaining reproducible results will appear clearly from a general consideration of the phenomenon of ignition. The true temperature of ignition may be defined as that "at which the reaction proceeds at a rate just sufficient to overbalance the loss of heat by radiation, conduction and convection from the burning layer of gases, so that the next layer is put in the same state and a steady combustion proceeds." It would appear from this enunciation how uncertain the temperature of ignition may be depending, as it does, on the various factors referred to above. For instance, the amount of radiation depends on the difference of temperature to which the soap bubble is brought before explosion and the temperature of the surroundings. Under increasingly insulated condition, therefore, the ignition temperature would decrease. The soap bubble method introduces, in addition to the factors mentioned

above, a dividing layer of steam between the source and the inflammable mixture. Under certain conditions either of the soap bubble or of the source, the magnitude of this dividing steam layer is infinitely small, but as will be shown in the experimental part, when the dividing layers assume any considerable magnitude, a corresponding difference in the ignition temperature is noticed. The effect of this "steam cushion" is to reduce the temperature which actually reaches the inflammable mixture. It is only rational, therefore, to expect under such circumstances ignition at a somewhat higher temperature of the source. All these factors may be included in what is termed as the preflame condition, the time-lag not excepted. In our experimental determinations the time-lag has been assumed to be absent as the explosion is instantaneous. The magnitude of the error that would be caused by slight time-lags can be realised from the latest experiments of Dixon in his new concentric tube apparatus (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1926, 22, 267).

TABLE I.

(a) *Ignition Temperatures of Hydrogen at Atmospheric Pressure.*

Lag (seconds). ...	0.5	1.5	2.0	5.0	10.0
In air (°C). ...	630	619	605	588	577
In oxygen (°C) ...	625	618	606	588	575

(b) *Ignition Temperature of Methane at Atmospheric Pressure.*

Lag (seconds). ...	0.5	0.6	1.0	2.0
In air (°C). ...	—	746	728	710
In oxygen (°C) ...	670	676	657	641

This feature of instantaneous explosion fundamentally differentiates McDavid's or our results from those of others, apart from the method of ignition. Further, on all other modes of ignition, the preflame condition exercises a more conspicuous influence than on ours.

The temperature of ignition was calculated in the same way as by McDavid, only a greater accuracy was aimed at. The source of ignition was produced in the following way: Silica or mica strips were wound round with platinum wires of different lengths and diameters. The coil was uniformly wound and heated

by a number of storage cells. The heating current was regulated by a rheostat, and an ammeter in the circuit indicated the constancy of the current. The relation between the current and the temperature was determined by placing minute crystals of well-purified salts and noting the exact currents required to attain the melting points of the salts. The salts used were potassium iodide (m.p. 687°), potassium bromide (m.p. 723°) and sodium chloride (m.p. 800°). The points so obtained were on a straight line, affording thus the means of finding out other temperatures with other values of the current (Fig. I).

FIG. I.

The reliability of such sources, with a little practice, was quite astonishing, as we could work for hours together with the same source without any alteration in its initially calibrated values. The ammeter employed in our experiments could read up to 0.025 ampere on the scale and 0.01 by means of the eye which latter corresponded usually to 3°—4°C. An error of 0.01 ampere in the reading introduced an error of 0.5-0.7% in the ignition temperature determination.

When the form of the source was altered to that of a simple loop of platinum wire or that of a sharply bent angle, the temperatures of ignition were found to be lowest in our series of experiments. The method of calibration was as usual.

The ignition temperatures of various mixtures of hydrogen and oxygen deserve special consideration in view of numerous ignition temperatures already recorded of such mixtures. Falk (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 28 1517; 1907 29, 1537) found by igniting mixtures of hydrogen and oxygen by adiabatic compression that the lowest ignition temperature is possessed by a mixture in which the two gases are in equimolecular proportions. From this he infers that the most active mixture is given by ($\text{H}_2 + \text{O}_2$) and not by ($2\text{H}_2 + \text{O}_2$), and concluded that in all hydrogen-oxygen combustions, hydrogen peroxide is first formed. He, therefore, considers the reaction between hydrogen and oxygen to be bimolecular which requires the active masses to be equimolecular for maximum velocity. Falk's experiments were conducted under high pressures (35-40 atmos.). Dixon, who repeated Falk's experiments after introducing several changes in the apparatus (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 105, 2036), found that with increasing proportions of oxygen, the ignition temperature of the oxy-hydrogen mixture decreases, but does not confirm that ($\text{H}_2 + \text{O}_2$) is the most active mixture as would be seen below.

TABLE II.

Composition.	Temp.	Composition.	Temp.
$15\text{H}_2 + \text{O}_2$	762°	$2\text{H}_2 + \text{O}_2$	526°
$10\text{H}_2 + \text{O}_2$	676°	$2\text{H}_2 + 2\text{O}_2$	511°
$6\text{H}_2 + \text{O}_2$	602°	$2\text{H}_2 + 8\text{O}_2$	478°
$4\text{H}_2 + \text{O}_2$	561°	$2\text{H}_2 + 16\text{O}_2$	472°
$3\text{H}_2 + \text{O}_2$	544°		

In our experiments two sets of results have to be considered in this connection: one, when the ignition source is a spiral and the other when the igniting source is a point. With a spiral, ($2\text{H}_2 + \text{O}_2$) is found to ignite at the lowest temperature, whereas with a point source, ($2\text{H}_2 + 3\text{O}_2$) ignited at the lowest temperature. The idea of determining the most active mixture from the lowest ignition temperature does not, therefore, seem to be at all reliable. This is also to be inferred from the divergence in results obtained by Falk and Dixon, both of whom used the adiabatic compression method, and as such, from thermodynamic considerations, the possibility of hydrogen peroxide formation was more to be expected

It seems probable, however, that up to a certain extent, increment in the proportion of oxygen lowers the ignition temperature. With a proportionately large source of ignition, the electrolytic mixture ($2\text{H}_2 + \text{O}_2$) ignites at the lowest temperature, and hence under that condition the maximum velocity of reaction would also correspond to a trimolecular reaction. This view would confirm Bodenstein's results who investigated the order of reaction between hydrogen and oxygen, leading their mixture into a red-hot porcelain tube, and concluded the reaction to be of the third order (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1899, 29, 665). Rowe (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1907, 59, 41), on recalculating Bodenstein's results, found the constants to agree just as well for a bimolecular as for a trimolecular reaction. He assumes, however, that since H_2O_2 is decomposed with very great rapidity at higher temperatures, it is incapable of being formed at all at these temperatures and that the reaction is therefore trimolecular. Fresh investigations to elucidate this point is in progress. It is noteworthy that the electrolytic gas ignites at the lowest current strength (temperature) whether platinum wire is wound on silica, porcelain or glass. In all these instances with increased proportion of oxygen the ignition temperature at first falls reaching the minimum at the electrolytic gas mixture, and again increasing with a rise in the percentage of oxygen. Using mica strips, however, for winding the wire around, the results are anomalous—with increased proportions of oxygen without passing through a minimum the ignition temperature rises. These results are shown clearly in Fig. 3. It has to be remarked, however, that the reproducibility of the above results requires some care and practice. It is hoped that by conducting experiments under more standardised conditions the soap bubble method would lend itself to greater quantitative accuracy seeing that our results are more concordant and more reproducible than those of McDavid's.

The subject is being further investigated from the point of view of the catalytic influence of the glowing wire on ignition temperature.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The soap solution employed in these experiments was prepared according to the method of C. V. Boys ("Soap Bubbles.") The solution was usually left in the dark for a week before use, which considerably improved its capacity of yielding larger bubbles.

The experimental arrangement is shown in Fig. II. The bubble produced at the mouth of the thistle funnel was brought in contact with the heated spiral or point, when instantaneous explosion was noticed at the requisite temperature. The experiments were conducted in a darkened room in order to be able to observe the appearance of the flame and to prevent any draught. The tables below give the results of a few of the large number of closely agreeing experiments with bubbles of twenty c.c. volume.

FIG. II.

TABLE III,

Diameter of Pt wire.	Length of Pt wire.	Ammeter reading.	Ignition temperature.	Composition of gas mixture (by vol).
0.3 mm.	16" (on silica)	2.84	767°	1H ₂ : 10 ₂
"	"	2.83	763°	2H ₂ : 10 ₂
"	"	2.81	756°	.. (Larger bubble 60 c. c.)
"	"	2.84	767°	5H ₂ : 10 ₂
"	"	2.9	788°	2H ₂ : 5Air
"	"	2.91	792°	1H ₂ : 3 ..
"	"	2.87	777°	1H ₂ : 1 ..
"	"	3.22	900°	1CO : 1 ..
"	"	3.18	886°	2 .. : 1 ..
"	"	3.225	902°	2 .. : 1 O ₂
"	"	3.29	925°	1 .. : 1 ..
"	"	3.21	897°	3 .. : 1 ..
"	"	3.16	873°	1 Coal gas : 1 air.
"	"	3.04	837°	2 .. : 1 ..

TABLE IV.

Diameter of Pt wire.	Length of Pt wire.	Ammeter reading.	Ignition temperature.	Composition of gas mixture (by vol.)
0.3 mm.	6" (on silica)	3.35	762°	1H ₂ : 1O ₂
"	"	3.33	758°	2,, : 1,,
"	"	3.34	760°	5,, : 1,,
"	"	3.67	846°	2CO : 1,,

TABLE V.

0.3 mm.	16" (on mica)	3.05	750°	1H ₂ : 1O ₂
"	"	3.025	742°	,, (Bigger bubble 60 c. c.)
"	"	3.02	740°	2H ₂ : 1O ₂
"	"	3.00	738°	,, (Bigger bubble 60 c. c.)
"	"	3.04	747°	5H ₂ : 1O ₂
"	"	3.43	882°	2CO : 1,,
"	"	3.37	862°	,, (Bigger bubble 60 c. c.)

TABLE VI.

(Point source)

0.3 mm.	3"	3.27	687°	2H ₂ ; 1O ₂
"	"	2.95	537°*	,, (Bigger bubble 60 c. c.)
"	"	3.61	843°	2CO : 1O ₂
"	"	3.48	783°	,, (Bigger bubble 60 c. c.)

TABLE VII.

(Loop source).

Diameter of Pt wire.	Length of Pt wire.	Ammeter reading.	Ignition temperature.	Composition of gas mixture (by vol.)
0.3 mm.	3"	3.32	683°	2H ₂ : 1O ₂
"	"	3.1	609°	,, (Bigger bubble 60 c. c.)

* Dixon and Crofts obtained by the adiabatic compression method an ignition temperature as low as 526° for the electrolytic gas mixture. The point source scarcely glowed, yet with larger bubbles there was explosion.

TABLE VIII.

Diameter of Pt wire.	Length of Pt wire.	Ammeter reading.	Ignition temperature.	Vol. of H ₂	Vol. of air.
0.25 mm.	22.5" (on silica)	2.27	785°	1	1
"	"	2.29	792°	2	3
"	"	2.30	797°	1	3
"	9" (on mica)	2.50	726°	1	1
"	"	2.52	732°	2	3
"	"	2.54	740°	1	2
"	"	2.57	750°	1	3
"	5" (on mica)	2.59	709°	1	1
"	"	2.64	725°	1	2
0.3 mm.	21.5" (on silica)	2.80	781°	1	1
"	"	2.825	788°	2	3
"	"	2.85	796°	1	3

TABLE IX.

Ignition of oxy-hydrogen mixtures by means of an electrically heated platinum point.

Gas-composition, (H ₂ : O ₂ by vol.).	Amperes. (a)	Amperes. (b)	Amperes. (c)
8 : 2	3.25	3.42	3.325
7 : 3	3.20	3.30	3.26
6.6 : 3.3	3.15	3.25	3.21
6 : 4	3.12	3.15	3.02
5 : 5	2.98	3.05	2.9
4 : 6	2.92	2.92	2.85
3 : 7	3.15	3.03	2.92
2 : 8	3.22	3.20	3.17

TABLE X.

Sources of ignition.

Composi- tion. H ₂ :O ₂	Pt wire wound on silica.			Pt wire wound on mica.		Pt. wire wound on porcelain.	Pt wire wound on glass.
	Amp.	Amp.	Amp.	Amp.	Amp.	Amp.	Amp.
	(a)	(b)	(c)	(a)	(b)		
8:2	2·925	2·89	2·785	2·64	2·65	3·08	3·3
7:3	2·9	2·88	2·775	2·66	2·67	3·02	3·29
2:1	2·895	2·87	2·77	2·67	2·68	3·01	3·285
6:4	2·9	2·91	2·78	2·68	2·685	3·02	3·29
5:5	2·91	2·93	2·79	2·695	2·69	3·025	3·3
4:6	2·925	2·96	2·8	2·725	2·7	3·035	3·315
3:7	2·96	2·985	2·81	2·74	2·72	3·05	3·325
2:8	3·02	3·01	2·83	2·76	2·77	3·06	3·345

These results are plotted below :

FIG. III.

TABLE XI.

The effect of size of the bubble on the ignition temperature, point source being employed in these experiments.

Composition of gas (H ₂ : O ₂ by vol.)	... 1 : 1	1 : 1	1 : 1	1 : 1
Vol. of the bubble in c. c.	... 60	50	30	20
Amperes.	... 2·66	2·73	2·79	2·82

This would indicate that size of the bubbles must be the same for obtaining reproducible and comparable ignition temperatures. Whether the lowering of the ignition temperatures with the increase in volume is due to the increasing thinness of the film or due to insulation considerations (*loc. cit.*) is at present not clear.

Summary and Conclusion.

(1) With decreasing length of wire, the ignition temperature decreases.

(2) The lowest ignition temperature is found with a point-source. There is a close agreement between this ignition temperature with large bubbles and the adiabatic ignition temperature.

(3) The larger bubbles give lower ignition temperatures due probably to the extremely thin film or to a more insulated condition of the inner gas mass.

(4) Mica being less conducting than silica, the ignition temperatures with mica strips are distinctly lower.